

Verbs And The Phenomenon Of Connotation In Them

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Abstract: This article describes the grammatical features of the verbs in English and Uzbek and the phenomenon of connotation in them. There are given some examples and usage of verbs.

Keywords — Verb, connotation, suffixes, prefixes, action, state, syntactic, lexical, component.

INTRODUCTION.

When we talk about the grammatical essence of the verb, it can be noted that, the verb is one of the main word categories, with its own meaning, grammatical forms and it is distinguished from other word categories by its syntactic functions. Verb work-action, process with determination of existence, state and attitude from the point of view of time connects with reality in style. It is with this feature that the verb is made of it different from a horse. The verb as an independent word category according to the following characteristics characterized:

1. Lexical-grammatical meaning in the quality of movement, state or process.
2. The distinctive self-making suffixes include the following suffixes (- ize, -en,-ify;) and prefixes (re, over -, out -, miss -, un;) as well as the lexical-grammatical word having morphemes.
3. Verb change words and make words than other word categories the reason for this is its many grammatical categories, which are much more advanced is owned by.
4. The connection of the verb in its own way.
5. Being able to come in different syntactic tasks in the sentence.

Verb-representing Action, state or process, tense, aspect, inclination, proportion, a word with grammatical categories such as perfect, modality and others category. Verbs are words that mean action. Action in grammar the meaning is very broad, and it has verbs such as to come (to come), to walk (to walk verbs that express actions, such as to wake up (to wake up), to stand (to stand representing cases, to astonish(surprise), to worry verbs such as represent mental changes, to blossom(bloom), to grow the biological processes that verbs like (to grow) represent, as well as a similar action and includes events. All this to specific private parties in addition to having a row, the side that is common to all of them is also existential, that is, they are phenomena that occur in relation to time is. The verb is an independent Word-series that refers to an action, state, or process, i.e. represents an action such as the appearance and transformation of a certain character. To the verb all such specific meanings help to distinguish it from other

word categories the general action that gives goes back to the meaning.

Yu.S.As Maslov points out, the verb is a sign that occurs over time, it is considered to be a Word-Series representing the grammatical significance of an action. The grammatical significance of action can be understood in a broad sense. He not only represents action and literal activity, but rather a state and a specific object or indicates the presence of an individual. For example:

A chair is a piece of furniture.

He wrote a letter.

He will soon recover

In English, verbs have grammatical categories and syntactic according to their external structure it is divided into personality and impersonal forms in a function-dependent manner. In either language that is, in both English and Uzbek, verbs are morphological, lexical-semantic, it is distinguished from other word categories by its lexical – grammatical features. Verbs in Uzbek are independent verbs according to their lexical – grammatical characteristics, and divided into auxiliary verbs. Independent verbs denote action, independent meaning able and in the sentence can come in the function of any of its branches. For Example: Filed the task was completed ahead of schedule.

Not only in Uzbek, but also in English, the noun, adjective, inflection of independent verbs forms of the name of the action, adjective, consonant, characteristic of its species there is. For example: Performance useful (Working is useful) action with auxiliary verbs does not express, does not express independent meaning. They represent different grammatical meanings it is used for or in another function. Auxiliary verbs have their main characteristics looking, serving to make a word and acting as a connecting verb auxiliary verbs, attached to verbs, that express different compound meanings is distinguished.

The verbs present in English are all of a certain morphological it is divided into two groups according to its characteristics. This is a certain morphological feature it is associated with the methods of making past tense forms and adjectival The first group includes proper verbs, and the second group includes false verbs. I.P.Ivanov, V.V.Burlakova and G.G.In their book, The pochepsovs described these two groups as what he calls the group of standard and non-standard verbs.

When it comes to the phenomenon of connotation, connotative verbs are also characterized by contextual (speech) antonymy, which manifests itself within a certain context by equating one action with another one, to the opposite, for example, You are able to embrace all created things with your thought, you could destroy the natural order with the power of your soul. (MY Lermontov, Vadim)

The opposition of the connotative verbs embrace - destroy lies in the positive meaning of the verb embrace, that is, "to embrace in full, comprehend, understand." Phrases The ability to embrace a thought makes it possible to assess the magnitude of the hero's thought. The verb destroy means "to disrupt, to build, to destroy" and has a pronounced negative assessment. Here, an irregular contrasting contrast is observed, which is of a singular nature and forms "inaccurate" or contextual antonymy, which contributes to a comprehensive description of the phenomena of objective reality, giving the text expressiveness, because information is easier to perceive when there is an overlap of opposite meanings.

Thus, the system-functional approach to the analysis of connotative verbal vocabulary in the conducted research contributed to the actualization of ways of reflecting non-linguistic reality in the word and explication of originality connotatives in the lexical and semantic development of the world.

The contextual approach to the analysis of linguistic material helped to identify not only the features of connotative verbal lexemes, but also the specifics of their existence as elements of the system of nominative means of the human lexicon, since it is in the context that the interdependence of semantics, syntax and pragmatics, epigrammatic, pragmatic and syntagmatic connections of lexemes is reflected

The conducted research allows us to say that the value of the connotative verb is manifested in its compatibility, which paradigm is subject to general semantic relations and depends on paradigmatic connections that combine lexical and semantic units of the language in a variety of ways In conclusion, the general conclusions are presented, the results of the study of verbal connotation as a macro component of the semantic structure of the verb word are summarized.

The study showed that connotations are inherent in all values due to indirect nomination, they do not exist separately from the meaning and are introduced simultaneously with it into the speech sequence. Connotative signs underlie reinterpretation words in systemic oppositions, which are the main tool for detecting components in the meaning of a sign, are distinguished by emotional, expressive, evaluative and stylistic components.

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